

Numerical method to extract differential features of news quotations in social media

Takaharu Tsuda

Abstract

There have been a number of researches to predict future business events with information sources on the internet, and they mostly utilize single or few information sources for prediction.

One reason of the low number is because it is not necessarily appropriate to assume that plural information sources have single characteristics in terms of authors, readers, opinions and so forth, which prohibits dealing all them equally. In order to utilize variety of information sources on internet as possible, it would be necessary to extract differential features of information sources, and evaluate how they relate one another. This thesis assumes that news from major Japanese newspaper publishers represent business facts, and blog and message board (hereafter 'social media') contain evaluation of business facts, and introduces concept model as well as experiments to extract features of the information sources (news and social media).

Specifically, this research hypothesizes that differential features are added in the social media's news quotation onto original news, and discusses how to extract the features in a numerical manner. It also discusses features can be at the level of information sources per se as well as at more granular taxonomy level. Entropy term-weighting and Naive-Bayes are adopted to categorize contents and singular vector decomposition is adopted to extract the differential features. Data relating to Toyota motors is experimented, and its finding not only supports the hypothesis but also exemplifies how differential features at granular taxonomy level represent the company's current characteristics.

1. Keywords

News articles, singular vector decomposition, Naïve-Bayes, text mining

February 20, 2019